

Field trial of the first G-PON, XGS-PON, 50G-PON triple-MPM reaching >35 dB ODN OPL with 20 km reach

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Abstract A triple coexistence G-XGS-50G-PON system demonstrates more than 35 dB of OPL with 20 km of reach. More than 41 Gbit/s downstream and 21 Gbit/s upstream traffic are exchanged in a field trial with commercial users, on existing 1:128 FTTH ODN in France. ©2024 The Authors

Introduction

50 Gbit/s-Passive Optical Network (50G-PON) will be the third generation of PON deployed worldwide in the coming years for Fiber To The Home/Enterprise/Antenna (FTTH/FTTE/FTTA). To avoid reinvesting in passive fiber infrastructure, the latest amendments of the ITU-T standards, G.9804 and G.9805, provided specifications for the triple coexistence of Gigabit-capable PON (G-PON), 10G-symmetrical PON (XGS-PON), and 50G-PON with a single transceiver Multiple PON Module (MPM) at the Optical Line Terminal (OLT). In 2024, specifications for Optical Distribution Network (ODN) losses as high as 32 dB (class C+) were released in ITU-T standard for both asymmetrical (50G/25G) and symmetrical line bitrate (50G/50G) options [1]. This progress is indeed of importance for operators as very high ODN losses (>32 dB) are reached in the field for legacy PONs, with additional 1:2 splitters being added to increase the PON split ratio, to a maximum of 1:128 so far. This aims to share network equipment more efficiently in deploying less ports and cards, and to demonstrate a reduction in CO₂ emissions when deploying a new technology (i.e XGS-PON in addition to G-PON so far).

A similar operation could be envisaged again to deploy the third generation of PON, meaning

that ODN Optical Path Loss (OPL) would reach 35 dB (class D) or even more [2,3]. To the best of our knowledge, in this paper, we demonstrate for the first time a commercial G-XGS-50G-PON system with a triple-PON Multiple PON Module (MPM) at the OLT, compatible with ODN OPL of 35 dB with 20 km of fiber reach.

Recently, a 50G-PON trial was detailed scientifically in [4] and announced the evolution of 10GE-PON to 50G-PON using a newly two-generation multi-PON module. Now, in this paper, in a field trial with commercial users, we demonstrate for the first time the compatibility of the existing FTTH ODN with a 1:128 split ratio capability, to host the three generations of PONs operating at the same time. More than 41 Gbit/s downstream (DS) and 21 Gbit/s upstream (US) Ethernet net traffic were exchanged over the 50G-PON system without any impact on the commercial services of G-PON and XGS-PON transmissions on the same ODN.

Lab experimental setup, results and discussion

Figure 1 represents the experimental setup used for the evaluation of the G-XGS-50G-PON system. A triple PON MPM was used in a line card inserted in a commercial OLT shelf which also contains an uplink card with two 100 Gbit/s uplink

Fig. 1: (a) Experimental setup for evaluation of the G-XGS-50G-PON system, (b) Optical spectrums of MPM and 50G-PON ONU1 output signals, (c) Optical eye diagrams emitted at OLT and at ONU1 outputs for 50G-PON, (d) Optical bursts from 50G-PON ONUs with 10 Gbit/s traffic per ONU and without traffic.

Fig. 2: (a) Ethernet Packet Error Ratio (PER) according to ODN OPL for DS **(a)** and US **(b)** PON transmissions in BtB and after 20 km of SMF.

interfaces. The MPM was connected to a typical FTTH ODN composed of up to 20 km of Standard Single Mode Fibre (SSMF), followed by a Variable Optical Attenuator to assess the minimal and maximal losses, and followed by an optical splitter 1:4 to connect 4 commercial ONUs: one G-PON, one XGS-PON and two 50G-PON ones. The optical spectrums of the MPM DS and 50G-PON ONU1 signals are presented in Figure 1(b). Characteristics of G-PON and XGS-PON ONUs are omitted from this paper due to their status as commercially available products with standard compliance certification. 50G-PON OLT and ONU1 eye diagrams, extinction ratio (ER), and output powers (P_{out}) as well as 50G-PON DS Transmitter Dispersion Eye Closure (TEC at 0 km and TDEC after 20 km) are shown in Figure 1(c), all showing standard specifications compatibility. An Ethernet tester was used to measure the Packet Error Rate (PER) in DS and US transmissions. Using the Ethernet tester, we measure in real time the number of packets lost over to the number of packets sent which defines the PER. With 1450 bytes long frames, we assume an error free limit when the $PER < 1.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ corresponding to a Bit Error Rate (BER) $< 1 \cdot 10^{-9}$ according to [2]. The following traffic configurations were set: up 40 Gbit/s DS and 20 Gbit/s US traffics between OLT and the 50G-PON ONUs, with Forward Error Correction (FEC) (Low-Density Parity-Check (L-DPC) coding 17280/14592 bytes); 8 Gbit/s symmetrical traffic on XGS-PON, with FEC (Reed Solomon block codes 248/216); 1 Gbit/s symmetrical traffic on G-PON, without FEC.

Figure 2 presents the DS (a) and US (b) PER evolution according to the ODN losses of each PON technologies, in back-to-back (BtB) and with 20 km of SSMF. For both US and DS transmission, error free transmissions are achieved for the three PON technologies over more than 35 dB of ODN OPL, which would correspond to a class D triple-PON MPM specifications. These results show quite significant progress compared to the state of art of 50G-PON systems [4], demonstrating more than 37.6 dB of OPL after 20 km of fibre

reach and 39.3 dB in BtB, in addition demonstrated here with triple co-existence. For this first 50G-PON commercial product, this can be justified by the implementation of L-DPC FEC associated to Digital Signal Processing and high-performance optics (low TDEC, high output power and extinction ratio transmitters, associated to low sensitivity receivers). Performances can be better after 20 km than in BtB when the signal is transmitted at wavelengths experiencing negative dispersion (wavelengths below 1314 nm in this SMF). The negative chromatic dispersion at 1286 nm then compensates laser chirp distortions, otherwise for wavelengths with positive dispersion, optical path penalties can be observed.

From an operator point of view, for the first time with this class D MPM, a split ratio of 1:256 could be envisaged when introducing 50G-PON in FTTH networks. However, increasing the number of ONUs per burst cycle may lead to unbalanced payload versus burst overhead traffic. Figure 1(d) plots the US optical bursts of the two 50G-PON ONUs with 10 Gbit/s of traffic, showing a zoom on the preamble length (worst-case specification is 610.9 ns). Overall, the two 50G-PON ONUs without sending any actual traffic already account for 1.4 μ s of time taken within the 125 μ s of the burst cycle. This total burst overhead duration (700 ns for each 50G-PON ONU) is not compatible with 1:256 split ratio, as the cumulated overheads will prevent from transmitting enough useful data. Burst overhead could be optimized by reducing the overhead value to objective specifications (205.8 ns), increasing the burst periodicity to 1 ms instead of 125 μ s in increasing the "Delay Tolerance" (DT) to 8 (as for G-PON deployed systems today) if US latency (estimated $>500 \mu$ s for DT at 8) is not critical for the targeted applications. Another approach to save some bandwidth in upstream for the payload would be to disable FEC for users connected with lower ODN losses. The ODN loss limits for which no

Fig. 3: (a) Field trial map and equipment involved in CO, ODN and user home; **(b)** Throughput (Iperf3) measurement of real-time DS and US traffics sent during the trial.

byte word was corrected by the US FEC are represented in Figure 2(b), showing a range of ODN losses below 28.1 dB where the US FEC can be disabled on all PONs (in the case of 20 km reach). According to data mining studies of a French FTTH network in 2020 [3], US FEC could be disabled for ~75 % of the users. As the FEC parity bytes represents 12.9 % and 15.5 % of the FEC block (the rest is the actual payload) for XGS-PON and 50G-PON respectively, disabling the FEC will provide more time for net traffic in the burst cycle to extend the split ratio to 256 users. Implementing a FEC code which adapts its parity to the optical path characteristics and quality for the remaining users would also optimize the net user bandwidth [5,6].

Field trial experimentation of 50G-PON co-existing with G&XGS-PON over operational FTTH ODN

The 50G-PON system was deployed in February 2024 in an operational central office in the city of Lannion, France, as represented on the map in Figure 3(a).

This OLT is connected to an operational ODN based on 2 stages of 2:2 splitters and 1 stage of 1:32 splitter in the street cabinet. This ODN already serves 48 G-PON and 1 XGS-PON users with commercial triple play services. The client hosting the 50G-PON ONU is connected on this ODN at a total reach of 3300 meters, with total losses of about 24 dB in O-band. To measure the capacity of the system installed on the field, 2 servers are used to generate and measure Transmission Control Protocol traffic via a throughput measurement tool called Iperf3: one at the OLT uplink interfaces (5 interfaces at 10 Gbit/s maximum capacity) and one at the 50G-PON ONU User Network Interfaces (2 interfaces at 25 Gbit/s). Figure 3(b) shows the mean traffic transmitted over the 50G-PON system, showing its maximal real time capacity at 41.2 Gbit/s downstream and 21.6 Gbit/s upstream between the user home and the central

office. No impact on G-PON and XGS-PON users connected over this ODN has been noticed during this trial. This demonstrates, for the first time in a field trial with real time traffics, the sustainability of FTTH infrastructures based on 1:128 split ratio to support the three generations of PONs in coexistence.

Conclusions

Beyond Class D ODN Optical Path Loss is demonstrated for the first time, to the best of our knowledge, with a G-XGS-50G-PON system based on a triple-PON MPM at OLT. Current limitations are due to G-PON and XGS-PON system performances that could be boosted at OLT side to reach the outstanding performances of the 50G-PON system which can support more than 39.3 dB OPL for short reach. To reduce operators carbon footprint, this opens opportunities to avoid tedious ODN reconstruction to address link budget issues and increase the PON split ratio, if bursts and FEC overheads are optimized to deliver the maximal net bitrate. Finally, for the first time, we demonstrate in a field trial the compatibility of existing 1:128 ODN with commercial G-PON and XGS-PON users to coexist with this G-XGS-50G-PON system, encouraging a smooth migration towards 50G-PON while maintaining the existing FTTH infrastructure.

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